

Name of IR: Maria do Rosário Sintra de Almeida Partidário
The Influence of Marine Protected Areas in Small-Scale Fisheries

Prof.ª Maria do Rosário Sintra de Almeida Partidário

The Ethics Committee of Instituto Superior Técnico (EC-IST) reviewed your application to obtain ethical assessment for the above mentioned project. The following documents have been reviewed:

Ref.	Documents	Version & date
1731699	COMISSAO DE ETICA IST_2023-02-0 TESE_Declaração de consentimento informado entrevistas_20240304.pdf	09/04/2024

The following members of the EC-IST participated in the ethical assessment:

Name	Role in Ethics Committee	Qualification	Gender	Affiliation to IST (Yes/No)
Mário Gaspar da Silva	President	Professor	M	Y
Isabel Trancoso	Member	Professor	F	Y
Isabel Sá Correia	Member	Professor	F	Y
Fernando Borges Araújo	Member	Professor	M	N
Miguel Prazeres	Member	Professor	M	Y

This EC-IST is working accordance to ICH-GCP, Schedule Y and ICMR guidelines, the EC-IST regulation and other applicable regulation.

None of the researchers participating in this study took part in the decision making and voting procedure for this assessment.

Based on the review of the above mentioned documents, the EC-IST states a favourable ethical opinion about the request / trial as submitted.

The EC-IST expects to be informed about the progress of the study, any Serious Adverse Events occurring in the course of the study, any revision in the protocol and in the participants' information/informed consent, and requests to be provided a copy of the final report.

Prof. Mário Gaspar da Silva
President of Ethics Committee of
Instituto Superior Técnico (CE-IST)